

LEADERSHIP AND TEAM PLAY – FORTE OF THE REGISTRAR IN COLLEGES OF
EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The paper expounded the views of scholars on the concept of leadership and team play and tried to contextualize the concepts within the realities of institutional administration in Nigeria. Similarly, the paper explored the dialectical relationship between management and leadership vis-à-vis their importance to professional administration. It highlighted the need for the delegation of duties by leadership. The theoretical framework of the paper was anchored on Tuckman's Team Theory of Bruce Tuckman in 1965, which identifies the five stages of team development as forming, storming, norming, performing and adjointing. The theory was used to evaluate the role demands and profile of the Registrar in educational institutions in Nigeria as a team player amid emerging challenges. The paper identified some of the forte needed by the Registrar to manage occupational challenges and to function effectively, such as emotional intelligence, use of the SMART principles, organizational skills, and directing skills. It equally discussed some notable challenges and practical demands on the Registrar as a leader and team player in institutional administration in Nigeria, such as: brain drain, digitization, staff redeployment, power relations and potential conflict triggers between the Provost and Registrar, re-designation and elongation of career paths for non-teaching staff, mentoring, and succession chain; as well as the place of merit in appointment and promotion with regards to the Peter's Principle as described by Laurence J. Peter. Conclusively, it elaborated on the confluence of leadership and management and recommended, among others: the need for the Registrar to be a talent-plus personality, develop the capacity to multi-task, be a team player by making conscious efforts to sell his or her vision to the subordinates, and always put the team before self.

Keywords: Leadership, Management, Delegation, Team Play, Registrar, Digitization and Mentoring.

Introduction

Beyond the normal academic discourse of viewing leadership and management theories as mental constructs, emerging realities and challenges of Nigeria's work cultures have greatly illuminated the need to further contextualize the two concepts of leadership and team play within the Nigerian setting to see how adaptable and suitable they are in developing the quality

pool and mix of knowledge workers and professional managers that possess the required skill sets and competitive edge to lead and effectively and efficiently manage the educational sector. This paper touches the nerve of the career challenges that many professionals in Nigeria (especially in the public sector) face while ascending the career track in their various organizations, i.e., the need to effectively manage and lead the team of subordinate officers to achieve the organization's goals. Managers or supervisors at all levels of the organization act as leaders because they have subordinates under them whose efforts have to be organized and harmonized. Everywhere people work in groups, the leadership function emerges, and there must be someone to guide that group. In succinct terms, leadership as an activity is common to all organizations.

A review of relevant literature shows much debate among scholars on how leadership differs from management. The general consensus is, however, that leadership involves management and management involves leadership, so it may be difficult to separate the two. There is also some consensus on the essential nature of both and the skills involved, but there is more disagreement on which is the most important.

The Global Community recently passed through a phase of change occasioned by the COVID-19 pandemic. This virus scourge threw many world economies into recession and altered the nation's occupational landscape, nature of work, competencies, scope of service delivery, human relations, value orientation, etc. Within the educational sector, a lot of workers became lethargic about work, accustomed to the lure of drawing monthly salaries without commensurate work, and have thus become somewhat change-resistant. Beyond the dialectic downside of the plague, however, more creative and innovative ways of getting things done became required of Professional Managers and Administrators. It suffices to note that managers and leaders alike had to think outside the box on many occasions to proffer solutions to emerging problems and challenges. The charge on Professional Administrators saddled with

the task of managing men, money, machines, and materials is to effectively and efficiently deploy the seven basic "F" anchors of good leadership in our human relations and as frontline managers of our institutions, namely: **friendliness, firmness, fairness, foresight, flexibility, forthrightness** and being **focused** on accomplishing set targets.

The scope of this paper is limited to the Colleges of Education (COEs) in Nigeria, given the broadness of the topic; hence the title: *Leadership and Team Play—Forte of the Registrar in Colleges of Education in Nigeria*. It is hoped that the paper will significantly stimulate the professional managers in the College of Education sector to refresh and reappraise their understanding and application of the two concepts to effectively attend to emerging issues in their daily work.

Leadership

Leadership means inspiring people to do their best to achieve a desired result. It involves developing and communicating a vision for the future, motivating people, and securing their engagement. Bhatia (2013) posits that leadership is related to a particular situation at a given point in time under a specific set of circumstances. Thus, leadership styles will be different under different circumstances.

The central theme of leadership is getting things accomplished through people. Schuller (1983) opines that leadership is the force that selects your dreams and sets your goals. It is the force that propels your endeavours to success. Similarly, Haimann in Bhatia (2013) defines leadership as the ability of a manager to induce subordinates to work with confidence and zeal. A good leader is ultimately a valuable addition to the organization or institution.

In a related vein, Shakespeare, in his popular quote, further identifies the notable ways of becoming a leader, which still hold true today. According to him, "Some are born great; some

achieve greatness; some have greatness thrust upon them; some purchase it; some win it by strength, force, or nepotism; some marry into it (becoming great as a result of marriage); some are elected; and some are appointed."

Armstrong (2012) identifies leadership skills as the ability to:

- Inspire others.
- Persuade others willingly to behave differently.
- Clarify what needs to be done and why.
- Communicate a sense of purpose to their team.
- Understand that they cannot create performance themselves but are conduits for performance through their influence on others.
- Get the team into action so that the task is achieved.

Onifade (2012) also identifies the following as the qualities of a good leader:

1. A good leader is one who possesses such qualities as accountability, vision, integrity, fairness, enthusiasm, flexibility, diligence, intelligence, honesty, and responsibility.
2. He should be able to initiate change.
3. He should be able to manage stress, conflict, and time effectively.
4. He must possess a good sense of judgement when taking decisions on issues.
5. He must be emotionally stable.
6. He must not only show interest in the organization but also in his subordinates.

According to Fayol in Bhatia (2013), a successful leader should possess the following qualities: health and physical fitness; intelligence and mental vigour; moral qualities; knowledge; decision-making power; foresightedness; and managerial ability.

Within the context of this paper, a leader can be adjudged exemplary when he possesses and exhibits in good measure the qualities that fit our mental construct and typology of who an effective leader is and provides the desired quality service delivery.

Management and Leadership

The word 'management' is derived from the Italian verb *maneggiare*, which means to 'handle a horse'. This definition at least states that to manage is to have charge of or responsibility for something, but there is more to it than that. Management has often been defined as 'getting things done through people' thus emphasizing its leadership component. However, managers are also responsible for guiding and controlling the business or their part of it by managing their other resources—finance, work systems, and technology. Management could therefore be defined as deciding what to do and then getting it done through the effective use of resources. Some commentators regard leadership as synonymous with management; others see them as distinct but closely linked and equally necessary activities; others consider management a subset of leadership; and yet others praise leadership and demonise management.

Mbieli (2006) posits that leadership is the chief tool of administrative management. He opines that in all spheres of human understanding, at home, in work situations, in social interactions, and in administrative and political institutions, different types of leadership exist to guide, direct, organize, persuade, motivate, and inspire others to work for a common interest. Certo (1980), on his part, tries to differentiate between leadership and management. He opines that managing is broader than leading and that while managing comprises both behavioural and non-behavioural issues, leading emphasizes behavioural issues. Certo avers that some managers could be leaders, and vice versa. To him, some managers are leaders, while some leaders are managers, but leading and managing do not have identical activities. In the long run, some effective managers become leaders. Not all managers become leaders in the short run.

Bennis (1989) viewed managers as those who promote efficiency, follow the rules and accept the status quo, while leaders focus on challenging the rules and promoting effectiveness. Kotter (1991) saw managers as being the ones who plan, budget, organise, and control, while leaders set direction, manage change, and motivate people. Hersey and Blanchard (1998) claimed that management merely consists of leadership applied to business situations; in other words, management forms a subset of the broader process of leadership.

The traditional model of what managers do is that it is a logical and systematic process of planning, organizing, motivating, and controlling. But this is misleading. Managers often carry out their work on a day-to-day basis in conditions of variety, turbulence, and unpredictability. Managers may have to be specialists in ambiguity, with the ability to cope with conflicting and unclear requirements.

Managers are doers. They deal with events as they occur. But they must also be concerned with where they are going. This requires strategic thinking, especially at higher levels. As strategic thinkers, managers develop a sense of purpose and frameworks for defining intentions and future directions. They are engaged in the process of strategic management.

The power relations between managers and workers thrive on a strong administrative system, which on the part of the managers and supervisors requires proactive and sound knowledge of the terms and conditions governing employment, a clear understanding of modern trends in people-centred management, and the deployment of tact in handling emerging tensions and conflict situations that may arise from time to time.

Leadership and Delegation of Duties

While it is a common belief among scholars that a good leader should be adept at multi-skilling and be ready to engage in simultaneous multiple assignments (SMA), the onerous demands of the leadership functions readily attest to the fact that no individual, no matter how gifted, can single-handedly undertake all the tasks necessary for the accomplishment of the organizational

goal. Oyeleye (2022) avers that there is a limit to the number of staff that a leader can effectively supervise. It is also not possible for him or her to be everywhere at the same time or know everything; hence the need for the leader to delegate part of the assignment to the subordinates with the capabilities to carry out some of the functions on his behalf.

Delegation of duties is therefore the process by which a supervisor gives out such, as part of his or her primary assignments to another person legally covered or accredited to carry out the tasks on his behalf (Oyeleye, 2022).

Mbieli (2006) similarly identifies the delegation of authority as the first principle of good leadership. A true organiser is the one who knows when and what to delegate. According to Mooney and Relley:

The real leader finds it easy to delegate authority, and he is quick to do so whenever he perceived it necessary, but he remains very conscious of the fact that there is one thing he cannot delegate, namely his own authority and the responsibility which it includes. It is in fact this very sense of responsibility which makes him so ready to delegate any task as soon as the total task begins to exceed his own unaided powers.

Delegation is an important managerial tool for getting things done through others by sharing authority with them. Within the context of this paper, it refers to the entrusting of authority to a deputy or a subordinate by the superintending officer. It enables the manager to distribute part of his workload to others and concentrate on other important functions, which he can perform better because of his skills and position in the organization. It means that when a manager delegates part of his job to a subordinate, he gives the subordinate the authority to carry out the task but retains the responsibility for the successful completion of the task. So, if the subordinate fails to complete the task to an acceptable standard, the manager, **not the subordinate**, is held responsible. However, the subordinate is accountable to the manager for

his work. Let me reaffirm that while authority can be delegated, the manager is still responsible and accountable for the results produced by the subordinates in areas where authority has been delegated to them.

Delegation helps in maintaining healthy relationships between the manager and the subordinates by clearly defining the authority and responsibility of the subordinates. According to Basil in Bhatia (2013), "Delegation can be one of management's best techniques for satisfying and motivating subordinates to better performance. In terms of technical aspects of business, delegation, through task assignment, can achieve faster decisions and eliminate cumbersome information systems. In terms of behavioural aspects, delegation can satisfy a person's demands for responsibility, recognition, and the opportunity to exercise authority."

Within the ambit of this presentation, the importance of constant teamwork among the manager and subordinate officers need not be over-emphasized. The acronym "TEAM" in this regard presupposes that '**Together Everyone Achieves Much**'.

Topchik (2007) defines a team as a group of individuals who accomplish designated objectives by working interdependently, communicating effectively, and making decisions that affect their work. They often have a certain level of autonomy, and they develop procedures for accomplishing their goals. Teams have a common purpose or goal and a clear mission statement for that purpose. Hence, they know what their desired results are, and their progress towards those goals can be measured.

An ideal team should have between five and 10 people. When a team is too small, there are not enough people to get the work done. When the team gets too large, communication and decision-making are difficult (Topchik, 2007).

Theoretical Framework

The need for a suitable theoretical paradigm to give this paper better insight and meaning cannot be downplayed; hence, this paper employs Tuckman's Team Theory, which identifies

five stages of team development, namely: forming, storming, norming, performing, and adjourning. The theory, which was propounded by Bruce Tuckman (a renowned psychologist) in 1965, holds that a team has to go through five stages of team development before it can fully reach its potential. This is especially true as it always takes time for a new team to get used to each other and each other's various ways of working.

A careful appreciation and synthesis of Tuckman's model of team development would significantly illuminate the critical importance of team play to the Registrar, who is desirous of effectively and efficiently discharging his schedule as the Chief Administrative Officer and custodian of records of his institution. Contextualizing the discourse of this paper through Tuckman's theory would enable us to reasonably spot the stages of our real-life experiences as Registrars in the College of Education system and how to prepare oneself for what lies ahead and how to tackle it.

The **forming stage** occurs when a suitable candidate is appointed to the prestigious office of the College Registrar and statutorily becomes part of the Management Team of the Institution. This career distinction is an interesting psychological moment, as team members tend to behave independently at this stage. While there may be good spirits and good intentions, the trust-building process has just begun, especially where the appointee is relatively new to the existing work culture and the College. A noticeable trend among Colleges is that many institutions, as much as possible, strive or prefer to appoint internal members of staff to such offices where vacancies occur and there are eligible staff. In line with the statutory dictates of the Registrar's office, it's important at this stage that the new appointees clearly understand the demands of the new office vis-à-vis the part they have to play as members of the Management Team.

The **storming stage** occurs after the initial excitement when the reality and weight of the onerous schedule of the office and the demands of the appointee's role as a distinguished

member of the Management Team stare him in the face. It is an emotive stage where egos and tempers may flare occasionally. The team members may disagree on how best to handle a task or voice their concerns. Team members at this point need to be tolerant of each other's views to maintain the stability of the system. The maturity, guidance, and objectivity of the Chief Executive of each institution as the team leader play a vital role in the team's development at this point.

The norming stage is the blending stage, where things tend to settle down for the team members. The Management team becomes a cohesive force and gets into the groove of working together as a team to achieve set targets. However, during the norming stage, there can still be a few overlaps with storming. As new tasks appear, there may still be some incidents of conflict. However, as the team members had earlier been through the worst part of some disagreements, it may be easier to address emerging intra-conflict situations.

The performing stage is where each team member understands everyone's strengths and weaknesses and is familiar enough with each other to help. Set targets aimed at actualizing the visions of the College are successfully accomplished at this stage. Each member is confident and motivated; hence, the team members can operate with less supervision. Ideally, at this stage, the members have high morale as they work in a supportive and cohesive team where creativity is encouraged and appreciated.

Similarly, **the adjourning stage** occurs when the appointee's team participation ceases. In social reality, this pawns out when the College Registrar comes to the end of his tenure of office and hands over to a successor. When the Management team has reached the performing stage and they have grown so close, there is often a nostalgic sense of loss among the other team members when such a performing team member exits. However, positive shared experiences among the team members make it easier when there are opportunities to work with some of the team members again in the not-too-distant future. It is also better managed

when the incumbent has successfully mentored suitable replacements for the vacancy to be created.

Profiling the Registrar

It is necessary at this juncture to profile the personality expectations and role demands of the Registrar in educational institutions in Nigeria, with a particular focus on the College of Education System.

1. The Registrar in the College of Education sector in Nigeria is the Chief Administrative Officer responsible to the Provost for the day-to-day administrative workflow in the College, except those bordering on financial matters, which fall within the purview of the Bursar. He generally supervises the activities of all Registry divisions as well as those of Registry staff attached to centres and directorates in the College.
2. The Registrar is the Secretary to the Governing Council, Academic Board, Convocation, and all statutory committees of the College and; advises on the rules, regulations, and procedures of the Institution. He is the custodian of the Institution's seal and other legal documents and records.
3. The Registrar also ensures the provision of quality secretarial services to College committees by Registry staff, the implementation of the decisions taken, and the collection, analysis, and storage of relevant statistics and information.
4. The administrative responsibilities of the Registrar's schedule with regard to academic work include providing staff for admission, registration, and matriculation of students, examinations, academic transcripts, advertising for entry into College programs and other courses, and the processing of staff appointments.
5. The Registrar is obligated by his office to carry out other official duties as may be delegated by the Chairman of Council and the College Provost.

A careful reflection on the highlighted profile seemingly gives the Registrar an eclectic personality. Unlike the physicians, who have set standardized referrals for diagnosis and treatment of patients, the Registrar is daily faced with establishment matters that are often unrelated in nature and scope and with limited information on precedence. He has to diligently research the books, consult, and deploy a good measure of emotional and native intelligence to address emerging issues without rupturing the occupational culture or peace. He is expected to always be a problem solver who can identify and anticipate problems and proffer solutions to them accordingly.

The Registrar's Forte

No textbook or manual can fully prepare the Registrar for life in the workplace, especially in terms of the professional relationship with others. Without diplomatic communications, though, the Registrar will be severely limited when it comes to handling the requests of colleagues and settling disputes effectively. This could lead to disagreements and challenging work situations that should not have been there in the first place. The Registrar requires a lot of diplomatic skills to effectively handle issues relating to the management-union relationship. Similarly, Aremu (2023) opines that Emotional Intelligence is important for leaders to be effective. Without it, an executive who has the best training in the world and limitless smart ideas would still not be effective. Emotional intelligence, according to him, is the candour and backbone of successful leadership. Therefore, a strong relationship exists between emotional intelligence and effective leadership performance.

Leadership thrives on the universal model of management popularized by the American Political scientist Luther Halsey Gulick under the acronym POSDCORB, which aptly highlights the following key functions of management: Planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting, and budgeting As leaders, the Registrar is officially charged with the management of the four (4) 'M's, namely: man, money, materials, and machines,

using the aforementioned functions. It is pertinent to look at some of these primary functions of management to have a better understanding of today's lecture.

Within the context of this presentation, efforts shall be made to illuminate three of these managerial functions, namely: **planning, organizing, and directing**, that I consider to be germane to effective leadership and team play. Institutions regularly make decisions on organizational matters, but before such decisions are taken, planning takes place, during which goals or objectives are set.

Planning in this context, is a rational and systematic way of making decisions. It is a kind of organized foresight with correct hindsight. An effective planning programme incorporates the effects of both external and internal factors. Cunningham (1982) classified this planning into strategic and operational decisions. When management is concerned with strategic decisions, these decisions must be taken in line with organizational planning, policies, and objectives. The operational decisions of the management on the other hand are concerned with employing effective and efficient means of executing strategic decisions.

For the Registrar in the Tertiary Educational Institutions to be an effective team player, he should strive at the beginning of the year to put in place a well-thought-out **work plan** for his department, which is largely derived from his experiences on the job as well as other intervening variables and foresight, covering critical areas such as routine demands, the approved academic calendar, the Council meeting schedule (as approved), staff appraisal, the submission of annual reports, etc. The foregoing should be done with due consultation with his Principal. The work plan would enable the leader to set attainable goals for the year and the means of achieving them. He would also be expected to sell his vision to his subordinates (especially his elite corps) at a strategic meeting convened by him, critique the feasibilities of the proposed work plan, take tactical decisions, and put in place mutually agreed structures for the accomplishment of the set goals.

For effective planning and goal setting, it is advisable for the Registrar to deploy and be guided by the **SMART principles**, namely: **S** – Is it sensible? **M** – Is it measurable? **A**– Is it achievable? **R** – Is it researchable/realizable? **T** – Is it time-bound?

Organizing: requires a formal structure of authority and the direction and flow of such authority through which work sub-divisions are defined, arranged, and coordinated so that each part relates to each other in a united and coherent manner to attain the prescribed objectives. Thus, the function of organizing involves the prioritization and determination of activities that need to be done to reach the organization's goal, assigning these activities to the proper personnel, and delegating the necessary authority to carry out these activities in a coordinated and cohesive manner.

Directing: The directing function is concerned with leadership, communication, motivation, and supervision so that the employees perform their activities in the most efficient manner possible to achieve the desired goals. The leadership element involves issuing instructions and guiding the subordinates about procedures and methods. The communication must be open both ways so that the information can be passed on to the subordinates and the feedback can be received from them. Motivation is very important since highly motivated people show excellent performance with less direction from superiors. Supervising subordinates would give continuous progress reports as well as assure the superiors that the directives were being properly carried out. The renowned entrepreneur Warren Buffett succinctly captures the critical role demanded of all workers to jealously protect his company's reputation:

'If you lose dollars for the firm by bad decisions, I will be very understanding.

If you lose reputation for the firm, I will be ruthless'.

The three aforementioned functions of management are closely interrelated. However, these functions are highly indistinguishable and virtually unrecognizable on the job. To effectively carry out these key managerial functions, the leadership of every organization requires a good

grasp of diplomatic skills in communicating the institution's vision, policy direction, and delegation of duties to subordinates and workers.

To manage the workers effectively, the manager has to interact with people to know the general tendencies of human behaviour and the factors influencing it. The manager should establish a good rapport, warm relationships, and conducive interpersonal relations with subordinates and peers. Diplomatic skills are needed to provide dynamic and effective leadership and build team spirit among employees. Managers should have opportunities to interact with their subordinates more intensely and continuously. Many managers get themselves so busy with their work that they find little time to talk to or listen to their subordinates, to guide them, to understand their viewpoints, to be supportive of them, and to develop them.

Contextualizing Some Challenges and Practical Demands on the Registrar vis-à-vis Leadership and Team Play in TEIs

Brain Drain

These are unusual times when managers of men are faced with the onerous task of providing leadership amidst the grim realities of dwindling income, hyper-inflation, outsourced municipal services, embargoed recruitment, scathing criticisms, and uninformed commentaries, as well as human capital flight or brain drain (referred to nowadays as 'japa', aided by frustrating connivance from some other staff with veiled motives). There is no denying the fact that the aforementioned brain drain has greatly depleted the pool of available professionals and quality hands in the system and daily threatens the succession chain. Notwithstanding, the common theatre parlance holds true in this regard... *The show must go on!*

Digitization

The world is a fast-paced, dynamic community of global convergence, especially with the advent of information and communication technology and its limitless possibilities. This has significantly altered the hitherto analogue culture of work. With the spate of digitization and evolution, the twenty-first century leader, who desires to be an effective and efficient manager, is not only required to be computer literate but also computer-proficient in adding real value to the institution. Endeavour to own a personal computer.

Beyond the quest and undue emphasis placed on "credentialism" in Public Service, an unhealthy and disturbing mindset commonly found among many managers in the TEIs is the notion held by some professional administrators cum managers that they have past the prime of personally knowing or directly applying computer knowledge to their service-delivery. This self-inflicted handicap often makes it difficult for them to effectively keep timelines and deliver quality work on given assignments. They are virtually and helplessly at the mercy of their subordinates, secretaries, and office assistants to get the job done. In as much as nature abhors vacuums, where such a leader fails to take charge, 'the tail would wag the dog.' Beyond the paper certification, personally seek to become proficient in the use and integration of information and communications technology into your work schedule and service delivery. It gives you a cutting-edge and valuable addition.

Staff Redeployment

In response to the organizational dynamics, there is always the need to keep the administrative wheel at optimal performance; it thus becomes incumbent on the leaders at some point in time to carry out the redeployment of staff as may be deemed necessary, especially in the Registry. In the Nigerian educational sector, redeployment is an Establishment term that connotes the movement of staff from one schedule to another on the same career path within the organization on some planned basis in order to familiarize such staff with different aspects of

the organizational functions, which would result in broadening his outlook and exposure to various management skills. Redeployment provides training grounds for staff. Here, they learn the values of interaction, human relations, and group dynamics. They get exposed to various viewpoints and tend to think liberally about how collective decisions are made.

As good and beneficial as redeployment is to the organization, it is equally fraught with some challenges, such as information diarrhoea, grapevine speculation, lobbying for perceived juicy portfolios, subtle and veiled resistance from some of the redeployed staff, ill-feeling, blackmail, polarization, etc. If not properly handled with the required maturity and tact, it can trigger some avoidable frictions with some heads of department and a frosty relationship between the Registrar and his Principal. It is always advisable that the Registrar, as a team player, in drawing up the redeployment list confer with notable heads of the Registry divisions saddled with the responsibility and, equally intimate clear the lists with the Provost before their final release. The ultimate aim of a healthy redeployment exercise is to ensure that people are dutifully engaged and the work demands are evenly spread among the available personnel.

Banjo (2013) opines that one notable area of friction between Registrar and the Vice Chancellor in the University system is the deployment of senior administrative staff. He posits that the Registrar should inform the Vice Chancellor before redeployments are made public, and in the process of the annual deployment exercise, he should sound out the heads of units to be affected.

Power Relations and Potential Conflict Triggers between the Provost and Registrar

The Provost is the Chief Executive Officer in the College of Education System in Nigeria, and statutorily, he is the leader of the Management Team. By occupational design, the Registrar is expected to maintain close working affinities and healthy relations with the Provost in order to keep the College system running smoothly. Permit me to share the two sides of the

elementary rule coin in institutional administration with you. **Rule 1 says: "The boss is always right", while Rule 2 says: "Where the boss is wrong, defer to Rule 1"**. In succinct terms, it can be safely inferred that the Registrar is saddled with the responsibility of advice, while the Provost, as the Chief Executive and Accounting Officer, has the powers of enforcement within the ambits of the Law. A clear understanding of the power boundaries from the foregoing could help enhance the relationship between the two Principal Officers and ultimately help to strengthen the bond, trust, and teamwork with the other members of Management.

Re-designation and Elongation of Career Paths for Non-Teaching Staff

Prior to the re-designation and elongation of the career paths of the Non-Teaching Staff in the College of Education System in Nigeria, the peak of most of the career paths had terminated on CONTISS 14, and many brilliant and resourceful workers had to contend with the brunt of frustrated aspirations and career advancement as only one officer could occupy the exalted office of the head for a tenured period. It was thus not uncommon to have occasional incidents of ill-feelings, misgivings among lieutenants, polarisation, diabolism, sabotage within the system, etc.

With the revision of the conditions and schemes of service for staff of Colleges of Education in 2015 and the elongation of the career paths of some of the Non-teaching Staff cadres to CONTEDISS 15, the accessibility to CONTEDISS 15 was equally expanded. This elongation of the career paths significantly and temporarily assuaged the degree of agitation among the Non-teaching Staff for equitable upward mobility. It also brought to the fore some dynamics and multifaceted dimensions of administrative leadership and participative management that require the appreciation and understanding of the Registrar. As the head of the Registry, the Registrar as a leader and team captain, should understand that among his colleagues, he is only the first among equals who is appointed by divine providence and put in a position of

trust for effective service delivery of the Registry. Hence, he has to explore all reasonable means to covet the cooperation and support of the elite corps of the Registry, especially the Deputy Registrars and the Assistant Deputy Registrars in order to foster a seamless and inclusive structure for probity and performance.

Mentoring and Succession Chain

Many managers get themselves so busy with their own work that they find little time to talk to or listen to their subordinates, to guide them, to understand their viewpoints, to be supportive of them, and to develop them. In succinct terms, a good leader is obliged to serve as a good mentor to his subordinates. Towards this end, he is expected to provide guidance, pragmatic advice, and continuous support that will help the subordinates learn and develop. Such mentoring would significantly help the subordinates perform better in the future and groom them for higher and greater things, i.e., career advancement. Mentoring can ultimately play an important part in a leadership and management development programme, especially in developing a healthy chain of possible successors.

Few leaders are successful unless a lot of people want them to be. No leader is successful without a few people helping them. Sadly, as soon as some people arrive at the top, they spend their time trying to push others off. They play king of the hill because of their insecurity or competitiveness. That may work for a time, but it usually won't last long. When your goal is to knock others down, you spend too much of your time and energy watching out for people who would do the same to you. Instead, why not give others a hand and ask them to join you? (Maxwell, 2008).

Peter's Principle

A notable challenge to leadership and management in many TEIs is whether appointment and promotion to leadership and management positions should be based strictly on merit, performance, or other extraneous factors.

Regrettably, a sizeable pool of professionals in the TEIs fall within the category that has been described by Laurence J. Peter under what is now commonly referred to as the Peter's Principle as having been promoted above their level of competence.' In candid terms, some of these workers have become square pegs in round holes, yet they are annually being promoted. 'It stands to reason however, that when the Plumber is given the Electrician's job, then it may not be an accident should anybody gets electrocuted'.

Best practice demands the use of a *proven track record as the best indicator of potential performance*. This is what employers try to achieve when they insist that job applicants state their *experience* in addition to their qualifications when completing employment application forms! *It is not right to promote a person who was blatantly incompetent at a lower job level, in the hope that he will be motivated to perform.*

Without prejudice to the profiling of eligible candidates and qualification criteria for appointment, many talented and potentially resourceful managers become very frustrated with the repeated denials experienced in their quest for career advancement and fulfilment. The demoralising outcomes of such endeavours seem to underline the often held belief that appointments are often not a true assessment of one's 'technical knowhow', but a combination of both '*technical knowhow*' and '*technical know who.*'

The Confluence of Leadership and Management

There is no gain in saying that effective management is a derivative of good leadership. To manage workers effectively, the Registrar has to interact with his staff to know the general tendencies of human behaviour and the factors influencing it. The Registrar is expected to establish good rapport, warm relationships, and conducive interpersonal relations with his subordinates and peers. Diplomatic skills are usually needed to provide this dynamic and effective leadership and build a team spirit among workers.

A poser often faced by many managers is how to distil the seemingly incongruent and dialectical relations between how a leader can **be firm** and **flexible** simultaneously to achieve effective management of the available resources. A good leader is obliged to always be firm and maintain the sanity chord on issues by taking informed, professional, and dispassionate decisions on them. In addressing emerging issues in the institution, however, an effective leader should know when to apply **Theory X** and **Theory Y** as propounded by Douglas McGregor in 1960. This theory is also commonly referred to as the carrot and Stick' theory and could result in greater efficiency on the part of the workers if appropriately deployed. Notwithstanding, it is also advisable for the leader to be open-minded and ready to yield to new and superior developments if and when needed.

Conclusion

Although this paper is not exhaustive on the twin concepts of leadership and team play, as there is no primer or master guide that can be used to create a one-size-fits-all model for successful leadership and team play in Public Service, especially in Tertiary Educational Institutions in Nigeria, it suffices to note that change has continuously been a constant factor in all human endeavours, and the educational sector is no exception. With global convergence, diplomatic approaches and skills in work organizations are regularly evaluated by researchers, and the frontiers of management practises are being further enriched to cope with emerging challenges.

Conclusively, it is obligatory for the management of each work organization to be pragmatic in its approaches and to always be in tune with current trends. Organizations and their managers must continually adapt to new situations if they are to continue to survive and prosper in the long run. A leader who wants to manage the situation successfully needs to take a chance, take charge, and take control! Schuller (1983) opines that taking a chance by itself is a reckless risk. Hence, when you take charge, you manage the risk. When you take control,

you manage your problems. One action is more valuable than a thousand good intentions.

Dare to take the bold step and earn the desired commendation.

Recommendations

The paper hereby recommends the following leadership and management nuggets for effective service delivery of Professional Administrators:

1. Clearly understand the mandate of the organization and be ready to invest in yourself and your vision. Regularly update and review your profile/resume in line with your vision.
2. Be a talent-plus personality as a professional manager and develop the capacity to multi-task. It is the hallmark of true leaders and a healthy way to secure your job. Such multi-skilling takes place when workers acquire, through experience and training, a range of different skills they can apply when carrying out different tasks (multi-tasking). This means that they can be used flexibly, transferring from one task to another as the occasion demands (Armstrong, 2012).
3. Be a team player. Make a conscious effort to sell your vision to your subordinates, and always put the team before self.
4. Build and regularly nurture the trust and confidence of your Principal.
5. Strive to understand and master the organization's politics. Every institution has its peculiarities, culture, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.
6. Be a positive change agent and a servant-leader. The servant leader strives to sincerely offer selfless stewardship for the collective good (John 13⁻¹⁵). The Rotary maxim equally attests to the foregoing that *"He profits most, he who serves best."*
7. Be flexible with your leadership styles and innovative in management, knowing that *using yesterday's formula for today's business may be a recipe for failure*. A leader

- should be flexible or open-minded, and be ready to absorb new ideas as may be demanded by the situation. The leader should be prepared to accommodate others viewpoints and alter decisions, if need be.
8. Develop a realistic annual work plan to foster the easy attainment of set targets.
 9. Be patient, discipline and keep a respectable distance with subordinates and co-workers. Maxwell (2008) posits that while *being one step ahead makes you a leader, it can also be bad, as being fifty steps ahead could make you a martyr.*
 10. Be proactive and pragmatic in generating and driving quality and sustainable policy proposals.
 11. Carefully and prayerfully put in place a team of trusted and tested professional advisers.
 12. In managing critical portfolios, a good and effective leader is expected to be knowledge-friendly by familiarizing himself with the acronyms or language registers in the Registry, handing over notes, and relevant subject files. Endeavour to read, regularly refresh, and master the Acts establishing the College, Public Service Rules, the Revised Schemes and Conditions of Service for Colleges of Education, the College Prospectus; Pension Reform Act; Procurement Acts, the Revised NCCE Minimum Standards and other relevant Acts pertaining to your job, etc.
 13. Be tactful and always deploy soft skills in human relations. **Be circumspect in utterances within and outside the organization.**
 14. Be a bridge-builder with an open mind. Understand and treasure the wisdom bite that "your worst enemy could be your best friend, while your best friend may turn out to be the cheerleader of your foes." Always call to mind the evergreen quote of William Shakespeare in Othello that: "*we cannot all be masters, nor all masters cannot be truly followed.*" The leadership portfolio confers on you the responsibility to tactfully

manage the ‘eagles’ and the ‘ducks’; carefully soak in the often twinned and patronizing information and misinformation from the grapevine, hasten slowly; lead by example, and deploy in good and balanced measure the five ‘F’s of leadership, which require that you be friendly, firm, focused, foresighted, flexible, forthright, and fair to all concerned. A good leader should always avoid treating issues in isolation, but rather seek out the antecedents.

15. Develop a strong shock absorber for criticism and a thick skin for scathing remarks, and be focused on your goal. It would always be there. *Always remember that when you get kicked in the rear, you know you are in front.*
16. As much as possible, maintain the goodwill of your predecessors in office. Sustain their past gains without necessarily re-inventing the wheel of administration. Know that all stories will ultimately become history.
17. Beyond applying sanctions and penalties, know when to commend your subordinates. A simple "thank you" can encourage good performance. A leader should possess a human relations attitude. The leader should be able to deal with people, secure their willing cooperation, and develop an understanding with them.
18. Diligently keep (with necessary backups) a good record management system. It may turn out to be your career's lifesaver in untoward, murky situations.
19. The leader should always strive for quality leadership and excellence in service delivery. This is very much attested to by Jessica Guidobono, who avers that *‘since every job is a self-portrait of the person who did it, we should always autograph our work with excellence.’*
20. Network with other colleagues from other institutions and professionally seek to cross-fertilize ideas pertaining to your areas of specialisation with them. No man is an island.

21. Regularly review your curriculum vitae to identify possible errors and update it with new additions.
22. Maintain a good and healthy balance between your career and family life.
23. Learn to manage executive stress. As much as possible, take your leave annually and take vacations.
24. Mentor subordinates and build their capacities for competition and succession. The greatest obligation of true leadership is to transfer its deposit to the next generation. Remember the administrative mantra, "We aspire today to inspire tomorrow".
25. Be humble and in taking decisions, be further guided by the core values of integrity and accountability as articulated in the National Ethics and Integrity Policy (2020).

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